

COMMITTEE ON TOXICITY OF CHEMICALS IN FOOD, CONSUMER PRODUCTS AND THE ENVIRONMENT

Overarching statement on risks of chemical toxicity and allergic disease in relation to infant diet

Background

1. The Scientific Advisory Committee on Nutrition (SACN) is undertaking a review of scientific evidence that bears on the Government's dietary recommendations for infants and young children. The review will identify new evidence that has emerged since the Government's current recommendations were formulated, and will appraise that evidence to determine whether the advice should be revised. The recommendations cover diet from birth to age five years, but will be considered in two stages, focussing first on infants aged 0 – 12 months, and then on advice for children aged 1 to 5 years. SACN is examining the nutritional basis of the advice, and has asked that evidence on possible adverse effects of diet should be considered by other advisory committees with relevant expertise. In particular, SACN asked COT to review the risks of toxicity from chemicals in the infant diet, and also what is known about the influence of infant diet on development of food allergy, and atopic and auto-immune disease.

2. The Government's current advice covers nutritional benefits and health risks associated with breast milk, formula milk, weaning and baby foods. It includes advice aimed at minimising risks of food allergy and allergic reactions to food, and advice relating to the toxicity of:

- caffeine,
- alcohol,
- methylmercury
- dioxins and dioxin-like compounds
- vitamin A,
- soy phytoestrogens.

3. In addition to these substances, COT identified a number of other chemicals, which might pose a dietary risk to infants, and for which advice might be needed. These were:

- phthalates,
- bisphenol A,
- aluminium,

- lead,
- legacy pesticides, including aldrin, dieldrin, endrin, chlordane, heptachlor, hexachlorobenzene, mirex, toxaphene and DDT.
- brominated flame retardants, including polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDE), hexabromocyclododecanes (HBCDDs), tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA) and other phenols, and polybrominated biphenyls (PBBs).
- the persistent organic pollutants (POPs) α - and β -hexachlorocyclohexane, lindane (γ - hexachlorocyclohexane), chlordecone, pentachlorobenzene, perfluoro octane sulfonic acid salts and perfluoro octane sulfonic acid, and technical endosulfan and its related isomers.

4. In considering whether current Government advice might need to be revised, COT made a preliminary assessment of the toxicity and allergenicity of each of the chemicals listed above, and of estimated exposures in infants through breast milk and other foods. Literature searches were undertaken to identify relevant scientific information.

5. In addition, a strategy was agreed for review of evidence on dietary exposures in infants and subsequent risk of developing food allergy, and atopic and auto-immune disease.

6. The use of additives in foods for infants and young children is prohibited except where it is for special medical purposes in the relevant age group¹. Therefore the COT did not consider food additives in its review.

7. This statement sets out the COT's conclusions regarding a subset of the chemicals identified for review. The remaining chemicals will be the subject of further statements, as will the influence of infant diet on risk of food allergy, and atopic and autoimmune disease.

Generic aspects of methodology

8. Estimates of consumption of breast milk and infant formula vary. In this statement, unless indicated otherwise, average and high daily intakes are taken as 800 mL and 1200 mL respectively. This accords with the approach adopted by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), e.g. EFSA (2011).

9. Where possible, estimated exposures to chemicals were compared to health-based guidance values – for example, Tolerable Daily Intakes (TDIs) established by the COT, EFSA or the World Health Organization (WHO). In principle, health-based guidance values are not applicable to neonates and infants less than 12 weeks of age (WHO, 2009). This is because very young infants are a potentially sensitive subgroup, their metabolic capacities not yet being fully developed. Risks in such infants need to be considered on a case-by-case basis, taking into account the basis of the TDI, and the likelihood that they might be unusually susceptible to the particular chemical under evaluation.

10. In addition to other forms of toxicity, an assessment was made of whether the chemicals under review might impact on the risk of developing food allergy or atopic disease. A chemical could itself be an allergen, inducing a specific allergic response, or it might have “adjuvant” effects. In an immunological context an adjuvant is a material that is able to enhance immune responsiveness without itself necessarily providing any specific

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/food/food/labellingnutrition/children/additives_en.htm

antigenic stimulus. More formally an adjuvant can be defined as any substance that can accelerate, prolong or enhance a specific immune response.

11. Evidence was sought first on whether chemicals or classes of chemicals were important allergens. Currently there are no regulatory tests that reliably distinguish chemicals with the ability to induce IgE antibody, which is the key biological mediator of food allergy (Kimber et al., 2011). However, it has been demonstrated that chemicals which provoke this type of immune response (IgE and immediate type hypersensitivity reactions) also give positive results in tests for contact sensitisation, such as the local lymph node assay (LLNA) (Dearman et al., 2012). Thus, a chemical which fails to register positive in the LLNA, or in other tests for contact sensitisation such as the guinea pig maximisation test, is extremely unlikely to induce either skin sensitisation or IgE responses.

12. Second, a literature research was made for evidence that the chemical induced allergenicity following dietary exposure. It should be noted that in contrast to other routes of exposure such as via the skin, oral exposure may down-regulate responses to known allergens. The best known example of this is nickel, one of the most common skin sensitisers. Oral contact (via orthodontic braces at an early age) was associated with a reduced frequency of later nickel hypersensitivity (Van Hoogstraten et al., 1991; Mortz et al 2002) as was nickel contamination of drinking water supplies (Smith-Sivertsen et al., 2002). This suggests that oral exposure to nickel and other chemical sensitisers may lead to tolerance rather than sensitisation.

Findings for specific chemicals

Caffeine

13. Caffeine is a component of widely consumed food products such as coffee, tea, chocolate and energy drinks. In 2008, the COT concluded that caffeine intake in pregnancy was associated with an increased risk of fetal growth restriction, and that it would be prudent to assume the association was causal. It was not possible to identify a threshold level of caffeine intake below which there was no elevation of risk, and it was likely that risk was increased in association with intakes of about 200 mg/day and perhaps lower. Data were inconclusive on the relation of maternal consumption of caffeine during pregnancy to adverse outcomes other than fetal growth restriction and spontaneous miscarriage, such as pre-term birth and congenital malformations.²

14. Based on that COT evaluation, the Food Standards Agency (FSA) advises pregnant women to consume less than 200 mg/day caffeine, and provides guidance on how that might be achieved for different foods and beverages. In addition, the Department of Health (DH) advises that breastfeeding mothers should avoid drinking too much tea or coffee (only occasionally rather than every day).

15. Estimation of total caffeine intake is complex due to the variety of foods and beverages containing caffeine, and the variability of their caffeine content. For example the concentration of caffeine in a cup of coffee or tea depends on factors such as the type of coffee bean or tea, the amount of coffee or tea used and the method of preparation.

16. Some studies have estimated potential caffeine exposure in breastfed infants. For example, in a study by Tyralla and Dodson (1979), after the ingestion of 150 mg caffeine

² <http://cot.food.gov.uk/cotstatements/cotstatementsyrs/cotstatements2008/cot200804>

by breastfeeding mothers, peak concentrations of caffeine in serum ranged from 2.39 to 4.05 µg/mL (mean 3.10, standard deviation (SD) 0.61) after 60 minutes, and peak concentrations in milk ranged from 1.4 to 2.4 µg/mL (mean 1.58, SD 0.45) by 30 minutes. In a single individual, doubling the dose of caffeine to 300 mg resulted in a doubling of the serum caffeine concentration at 30 and 60 minutes (values of 5.80 and 6.50 µg/mL respectively). In breast milk, caffeine levels after the 300 mg dose were nearly double the levels after 150 mg at 30 min, and more than double at 120 min. The increase in caffeine ingestion did not alter the milk to serum ratios.

17. In a study by Ryu et al. (1985a), breastfeeding mothers drank five cups (about 180mL per cup) of decaffeinated coffee plus 750 mg of caffeine each day for five days, which resulted in an average caffeine concentration in breast milk of 4.3 µg/mL. From this concentration, Ryu estimated that an infant could receive 0.6-0.8 mg/kg bodyweight (bw) per day caffeine, assuming milk consumption of 150-180 mL/kg bw per day. In a second study (Ryu et al., 1985b), the caffeine intake of infants was estimated to be 0.3-1.0 mg/kg bw per day, which was 0.6-1.9 % of the quantity of caffeine consumed by the mother (500 mg/day over 5 days). These percentages are similar to the 0.06-1.5 % of maternal dose estimated by Berlin et al. (1984). No physiological changes such as alteration in sleep pattern or modulation of heart rate, were reported in breastfed infants at maternal intakes of 500 mg/day over 5 days (Ryu et al, 1985b).

18. A cross-sectional investigation of 19 breastfed infants aged 4 days to 19 weeks, whose mothers had consumed a single dose of caffeine (145.8 mg), found that the highest level of caffeine in saliva was 0.75 µg/mL in an infant aged between 14 and 20 days. The mother with the highest concentration of caffeine in breast milk (1.22 µg/mL) had the infant with the highest daily caffeine intake (0.20 mg/kg bw/day) (Hildebrandt et al., 1983). Means, medians and measures of individual variation were not reported, nor was the daily consumption of breast milk, but the estimated exposure would be consistent with an intake of 800 mL. No health effects were described at these levels of exposure,

19. In a small study, a total of 10 doses of caffeine citrate (10 mg/kg b.w.), eight administered intravenously and two orally, were given to each of seven infants recruited at ages ranging from 2½ weeks to 6 months (Aranda et al., 1979). With increasing age, a progressive reduction in half-life was observed for the disappearance of caffeine from plasma. Plasma half-life shortened from 80 h at 1 to 2½ months of age to become similar to that of an adult (14.2 h) at 4-6 months. This could be explained by the maturation of CYP1A2, the activity of which is negligible in the fetus (Pelkonen et al., 1973).

20. CYP1A1 and CYP1A2 are absent in the human fetal liver whilst the presence of CYP3A suggests that the metabolic pathways of caffeine depend on this enzyme before birth (Cazeneuve et al., 1994). CYP1A2 has been reported to be responsible for more than 95% of the primary metabolism of caffeine after birth (Kalow and Tang, 1993) and its activity gradually increases from birth (0.12 nmol/min/mg microsomal protein) up to the age group of 1 to 15 years old (1.10 nmol/min/mg microsomal protein) (Alcorn and McNamara, 2003).

21. No reports were identified which suggested that dietary caffeine is allergenic.

22. The COT concluded that breastfed infants can be exposed to caffeine if their mothers consume caffeine-containing foods and beverages, but that the available scientific evidence did not demonstrate a consequent health risk in infants. The Committee noted that the basis for the Government's current advice to breastfeeding mothers on caffeine

consumption was extrapolated from that provided to pregnant women, and the available information did not provide a basis for refining it.

Alcohol

23. Alcohol is widely consumed in the UK population. Moreover, it has been reported that levels of alcohol in breast milk are close to those in the mother's blood stream³.

24. Currently, the Government advises that breastfeeding women should drink no more than 1 or 2 units of alcohol once or twice a week. One unit is 10 mL (8 g) of pure ethanol.

25. A few studies have looked at effects in infants exposed to alcohol through breast milk. Two investigations aimed to provide an alcohol dose of 0.3 g/kg b.w. to breastfeeding women (equivalent to 21 g, or about 2.5 units, for a 70kg woman) on two separate occasions one week apart. In one study, Mennella and Beauchamp (1991) reported disruption of sleeping patterns, agitation and sedative effects in the infants, the nature of effects depending on time after intake. In the other, Chien et al. (2009) reported reduced breast milk consumption, which could have been due to altered taste and/or decreased release of milk to the nipple.

26. More serious detrimental health effects occur in infants after frequent high maternal intakes of alcohol. For example, a study in Mexico reported a negative correlation between consumption by breastfeeding mothers (n = 57) of pulque (a traditional Mexican alcoholic beverage) and infants' growth and weight gain. The median maternal alcohol intake was 17.8 g/day, and for two high level consumers the intake was over 57.1 g/day (Backstrand et al., 2004). The range of intakes in the group was some 2-7 units per day. Another report describes a clinical pattern resembling that of Cushing syndrome in an infant who consumed breast milk containing 10 g/L alcohol as a result of its mother consuming 10 drinks, containing a total of 100g alcohol, per day (Giglia and Binns, 2006).

27. Alcohol is used as a vehicle for the LLNA and does not stimulate positive responses (Ikarashi et al., 1992). No reports were found suggesting that alcohol is allergenic.

28. The COT concluded that current Government advice was supported by reports of minor behavioural effects in breastfed babies after mothers had consumed approximately 2.5 units of alcohol on two occasions one week apart, and of more serious effects following daily consumption at higher levels. No reason was found to change the advice.

Methylmercury

29. Methylmercury (MeHg) has been of concern because of its neurodevelopmental toxicity, which has prompted advice regarding consumption by pregnant women and children of fish that contain high levels of MeHg.

30. The most recent COT opinion on MeHg in 2004 concluded that the provisional tolerable weekly intake (PTWI) of 1.6 µg/kg bw established by the Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives (JECFA) in 2003 was sufficient to protect against neurodevelopmental effects in the fetus, and should be used in assessing risks from dietary exposure to MeHg in women who are pregnant or may become pregnant within the

³ <http://www.drinkaware.co.uk/alcohol-and-you/family/alcohol-and-breastfeeding>

following year.⁴ For the wider population, a guideline value of 3.3 µg/kg bw/week was considered sufficiently protective. Using the pharmacokinetic model employed by the JECFA in its 2003 evaluation, and assuming a maternal body weight of 65 kg, the COT judged that an infant would not exceed the PTWI through exclusive breastfeeding if maternal MeHg intake was less than 9.5 µg/kg bw/week. The COT therefore concluded that a guideline of 3.3 µg/kg bw/week was also appropriate for breastfeeding mothers since this would result in intakes by breastfed infants that were below the PTWI of 1.6 µg/kg bw. The COT further advised that regular consumption of certain types of fish could result in these guideline values being exceeded.

31. Based on those COT conclusions, the Government currently advises that breastfeeding mothers should avoid eating more than one portion of shark, swordfish or marlin per week, and that children should avoid eating these species.

32. There is a higher risk of adverse effects on the fetus during gestation than on infants through breastfeeding because there is no effective placental barrier to MeHg, whilst transfer from mother's blood to breast milk is more limited. Some studies have recorded a decline in blood levels during the first months after birth, indicating that post-natal exposure is lower than that pre-natally. For example, Björnberg et al. (2005) found a decline in the levels of mercury in blood in the period from birth (median 0.09 µg/L) to age 13 weeks (median 0.05 µg/L) in a Swedish cohort. Similarly Sakamoto et al., (2002) demonstrated nearly 50% lower levels of mercury in red blood cells from Japanese infants aged 3 months (5.8 ng/g) when compared with levels found in cord blood.

33. In a survey on commercial weaning food and formula milk in the UK (FSA, 2006), MeHg was found at concentrations at or above the limit of detection (LOD) in only five of the eleven samples analysed, all of which contained fish. The mean total mercury and MeHg concentrations in all samples were 0.020 mg/kg and 0.010 mg/kg respectively, with an average of 46% of the total mercury in the form of MeHg. The highest level of MeHg was 0.025mg/kg. Estimated dietary exposures to mercury from these foods were 0.03-0.07 µg/kg bw/day, which was well below the PTWI of 1.6 µg/kg bw (equivalent to 0.23 µg/kg bw/day).

34. There is some evidence of immunogenicity triggered by subcutaneous administration of MeHg to mice, with induction of lymphocyte proliferation and provocation of IgE antibody responses, although MeHg was considerably less effective than mercury chloride in inducing IgE (Hultman et al., 1999; Stiller-Winkler et al, 1988). No reports of allergenicity from dietary exposure to methylmercury were identified.

35. The Committee noted that EFSA was currently evaluating mercury and MeHg, and agreed to wait until the EFSA opinion is published before deciding whether further review of MeHg is required.

Dioxins and dioxin-like compounds

36. Dioxin-like compounds include polychlorinated dibenzodioxins (PCDDs), polychlorinated dibenzofurans (PCDFs) and certain polychlorinated biphenyls that exhibit dioxin-like activity (DL-PCBs). These chemicals are classified as POPs. They are lipophilic, bioaccumulate in fat, are transferred to milk, and are excreted very slowly.

⁴<http://cot.food.gov.uk/cotstatements/cotstatementsyrs/cotstatements2004/cotstatements2004mercury>

37. In 2001, the COT established a TDI of 2 pg WHO-TEQ⁵/kg bw for PCDDs, PCDFs and DL-PCBs, based on reproductive effects of dioxins in offspring, dependent on maternal body burden. The Committee noted at that time that due to their very long half-lives in humans, assessment of the effects of dioxin-like compounds should be based on body-burden rather than external dose, and that short-term exceedances of the TDI would not be expected to result in adverse effects⁶. The COT has also advised that regular consumption of certain types of oily fish could result in the TDI being exceeded.⁷

38. Based on those COT conclusions, the Government advises that breastfeeding mothers and girls should not eat more than two portions of oily fish per week, and that boys should not eat more than four portions of oily fish per week.

39. The World Health Organization (WHO) has sponsored three surveys of PCDD/Fs and DL-PCBs in human milk, in 1987-1988, 1992 -1993 and 2000. A general downward trend in the levels of dioxin-like compounds in breast milk was observed, as is illustrated in Table 1 for those countries that participated in all three surveys.

Table 1. Dioxin concentrations in human milk (from van Leeuwen et., 2002).

Survey years	WHO-TEQ (pg/g fat)		
	1987-1988	1992-1993	2000
The Netherlands	39	26	18
Germany	37	19	11
Finland	19	19	9
Norway	19	12	7
Croatia	13	12	6
Hungary	10	9	7

40. More recently, Ulazewska et al. (2011) collated data on levels of PCDD/PCDF and DL-PCB in breast milk in several Italian cities, and reported a continuing reduction over time. The concentrations reported were approximately 24 and 4 pg WHO-TEQ/g fat in 1987 and 2009 respectively for PCDD/Fs, and 16 and 5 pg WHO-TEQ/g fat for DL-PCBs in 2001 and 2009 respectively.

41. Similarly, a study of more than 1000 human breast milk samples collected over several decades in Germany demonstrated that PCDD/F levels decreased considerably

⁵ TEQ = Toxic Equivalent. The TEQ is defined as the sum of the products when the concentration of each dioxin-like compound is multiplied by its Toxicity Equivalency Factor (TEF). The TEF values relate the potency of the less toxic dioxin-like compounds to that of the most toxic, 2,3,7,8-TCDD. When TEF values set by the WHO in 1998 are applied, the resulting overall concentrations are referred to as WHO-TEQs. A re-evaluation of TEFs by WHO in 2005 resulted in changes in some of the values, and the TEQs using these values are referred to as WHO₂₀₀₅-TEQs.

⁶ <http://cot.food.gov.uk/pdfs/cotstatementdioxins200702.pdf>.

⁷ <http://cot.food.gov.uk/cotreports/cotjointreps/sacnfishconsumption>
<http://cot.food.gov.uk/cotstatements/cotstatementsyrs/cotstatements2006/cotstatement2006fishsurveys>

over time. Median levels were approximately 34 pg I-TEQ/g fat in 1989 and 10 pg I-TEQ/g fat in 2003 (Fürst, 2006). These concentrations were estimated to result in exposures through breastfeeding that decreased from approximately 190 pg I-TEQ/kg bw. in 1989 to 60 pg I-TEQ/kg bw in 2003. Several other studies have confirmed a decline over time in the concentrations of dioxin-like compounds in human milk (Noren and Meironyte, 2000; Bates et al., 2002; Kunisue et al., 2006; Polder et al., 2003; Polder et al., 2008; Raab et al., 2008).

42. This fall is widely considered to result from preventive measures employed over recent decades to reduce or eliminate POPs in the environment (Van Leeuwen and Malish, 2002).

43. In the past 10 years only one study has addressed infants' exposure to dioxins in breast milk in the UK. Known as the SUREmilk pilot study, this explored methods for the recruitment, collection, storage and management of an archive of breast milk samples. The study took the opportunity to carry out analytical measurements of a number of environmental contaminants, including dioxins and DL-PCBs. Primiparous pregnant women and mothers aged 16 to 42 years (mean 28 years) were recruited in Yorkshire during 2001-2002. One or more breast milk samples were taken between the first and 16th week of lactation. The results (Table 2) were reviewed by the COT in 2004, which concluded that *“Taking into account that the TDI is now set to protect against reproductive effects and the evidence that concentrations of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs in breast milk are declining, the new data do not suggest any reason to alter Government advice that breastfeeding should continue to be encouraged on the basis of convincing evidence of the benefits of human milk to the overall health and development of the infant”*⁸.

Table 2. Estimated dietary exposures of infants to dioxins and DL-PCBs (from COT, 2004)

Age (months)	Mean consumption of breast milk (g/kg bw/d)	Estimated <i>upper bound</i> dietary intakes of dioxins + DL-PCBs (pg WHO-TEQ/kg bodyweight/day)		
		Human milk		Baby foods
		Suremilk Pools A-Z	1993/94	2003
< 2	160	46-125 (mean 83)	186	
2-3	140	41-109 (mean 72)	163	
3-4	124	36-97 (mean 64)	144	
4-5	103	30-80 (mean 53)	120	
5-6	79	23-62 (mean 41)	92	0.3-0.4
6-7	63	18-49 (mean 33)	73	
7-8	42	12-33 (mean 22)	49	
8-10	37	11-29 (mean 19)	43	0.4

44. In relation to the weaning diet, the latest data from monitoring of dioxins and PCBs in food and feed by EFSA, covering the period 1995-2010, indicated that infants were less exposed than toddlers and other children, with an average exposure of around 1.1 pg TEQ-WHO₂₀₀₅/kg b.w. per day (EFSA, 2012). This estimate was based on levels of dioxins in 33 food and feed groups covering a substantial part of the human diet, and particularly those food and feed groups in which historically there have been major occurrences of dioxins. The report did not take into account exposure from breast milk. The major

⁸ <http://cot.food.gov.uk/cotstatements/cotstatementsyrs/cotstatements2004/cotstatebreastmilk>

contributors to the estimated total exposure in infants were milk and dairy products (27.5-49.6 %) followed by “foods for infants and young children” (21.7-30.9 %).

45. Dioxins are immunosuppressive and inhibit lymphocyte proliferation (Lundberg et al., 1991), and no reports of allergenic responses to dioxins in diet were identified. Therefore dioxins are not considered to be allergenic.

46. While the TDI for dioxins and dioxin-like compounds is exceeded during breastfeeding, there is a well-established declining trend in exposure during the first year of life, as shown in Table 2. Dietary exposures from weaning foods are much lower than from breast milk. The COT has previously noted that the health implications of exceeding the TDI at an early age were not clear. The TDI was based on effects in the developing male reproductive system related to maternal body burden, and there was uncertainty as to whether similar effects would result from post-natal exposure. However, there was no basis for assuming that the young infant was at elevated risk. Furthermore, there was evidence that the half lives of dioxin and certain PCDFs in young children were considerably shorter than in adults⁹. Therefore exceedance of the TDI for a short period of time in infancy and early childhood does not imply a health risk.

47. Given the decreasing occurrence of dioxin-like chemicals in breast milk and lower dietary exposures from infant formula and weaning foods, the COT concluded that there was no need to change current advice on breastfeeding or infant feeding in order to protect against these chemicals.

Phthalates

48. Phthalates were selected for consideration because they are widely used in consumer products and may be present in food due to environmental contamination or release from plastic food packaging. Phthalates were analysed in the UK total diet study (TDS) which examined 20 food groups, and a number of phthalates were detected in cereals, bread, nuts, meat products, fish, sugars and preserves, oils and fats (FSA, 2012).

49. The COT recently endorsed a number of TDIs for phthalate esters that had been established by EFSA or the WHO¹⁰. For diethylhexylphthalate (DEHP), a TDI of 50 µg/kg bw had been set by EFSA (EFSA, 2005a), based on a NOAEL of 5 mg/kg bw/day for testicular toxicity and developmental toxicity, and using an uncertainty factor of 100. For dibutylphthalate (DBP) EFSA had established a TDI of 10 µg/kg bw, based on a LOAEL of 2 mg/kg bw/day and an uncertainty factor of 200 (twice the default factor of 100 because the TDI was derived from a LOAEL) (EFSA, 2005b). For butylbenzylphthalate (BBP), a TDI of 500 µg/kg bw had been set, based on a NOAEL of 50 mg/kg bw/day for testicular toxicity with an uncertainty factor of 100 (EFSA, 2005c). For diethylphthalate (DEP) a TDI of 500 µg/kg bw/day had been proposed by WHO, based on a NOAEL of 1600 mg/kg bw/day for developmental effects (intraperitoneal administration), with an uncertainty factor of 300 (including a factor of 3 for incompleteness of the database) (WHO, 2003). TDIs have not been established for disobutylphthalate (DiBP) or dioctylphthalate (DOP).

50. A small number of publications relate to phthalates in breast milk or infant formula. In a report of the Bavarian Monitoring of Breast Milk study (Fromme et al., 2011), the mean (95th percentile) concentrations measured in breast milk were 5.1 (13.5) µg/L DEHP, 1.2 (3.1) µg/L DBP and 1.5 (4.3) µg/L DiBP. Another study undertook measurements of phthalates in breast milk of Swedish women (Hogberg et al., 2008). The mean and

⁹ <http://cot.food.gov.uk/cotstatements/cotstatementsyrs/cotstatements2006/cotstatement2006dioxintef>

¹⁰ <http://cot.food.gov.uk/pdfs/cotstatementphthalates201104.pdf>

standard deviation (SD) concentrations reported were 0.30 (SD 0.24) µg/L DEP, 2.8 (SD 3.4) µg/L DBP, 0.75 (SD 0.80) µg/L BBP, 17 (SD 47) µg/L DEHP and 1.1 (SD 2.3) µg/L DOP.

51. Assessment of exposures from mean concentrations in breast milk is considered appropriate, since the effects of phthalates are chronic not acute, they are not accumulative, and levels in breast milk are likely to vary from day to day, depending on a mothers' exposures. At the highest identified mean concentration for any of the individual phthalates, i.e. 17.0 µg/L of DEHP, an infant with average breast milk consumption of 800 mL/day, would have an exposure of 2.7 µg/kg bw per day, while a high consumption of 1200 mL/day would provide an exposure of 4.1 µg/kg bw per day. Both of these values are considerably below the TDI of 50 µg/kg bw. Estimated intakes of the other phthalates individually would similarly be below their respective TDIs.

52. The COT has previously concluded that a cumulative approach should be taken when assessing health risks from phthalates. Cumulative exposure from breast milk was calculated by adding estimated exposures to individual phthalates, derived from the mean concentration for each, and assuming consumptions of average (800 mL) or high (1200 mL) amounts of breast milk by a 5 kg infant. Based on the concentrations found in Fromme's study, the estimated combined exposures were 1.2 µg/kg bw/day and 1.9 µg/kg bw/day, for the sum of DEHP, DBP and DiBP, with average and high level consumption of breast milk, respectively. Using the occurrence data reported in Hogberg's study on Swedish women, combined exposures of 3.5 µg/kg bw/day and 5.29 µg/kg bw/day were estimated for the sum of DEP, DBP, BBP, DEHP and DOP, with average and high level consumption, respectively. These estimated exposures are all below the lowest TDI established for any individual phthalate, which is 10 µg/kg bw for DBP.

53. In a review of data from 27 samples of powdered infant formula in different countries, DBP and DEHP were detected in all samples, with higher levels of DEHP (34 to 280 ng/g) than of DBP (15 to 77 ng/g). The highest concentration of DEHP was in a sample from Turkey, and the highest concentration of DBP was in a sample from Japan (Cao, 2010). If formula containing 280 µg/kg DEHP were consumed by an average (800 mL) and a high-consuming infant (1200 mL), the exposures would be about 45 and 67 µg/kg bw/day respectively. The latter is above the TDI (50 µg/kg bw) established for DEHP. If formula containing 77 µg/kg DBP were consumed by an average and a high consumer, the exposures would be about 12.3 and 18.5 µg/kg bw/day respectively, both of which exceed the TDI of 10 µg/kg bw established for DBP. The data presented in the review by Cao do not allow estimation of cumulative exposure, and it is not clear if the reported levels are relevant to formula milk in the UK.

54. EFSA reported estimated exposures of infants older than 6 months to DEHP, DBP and BBP from infant formula plus ready-to-use baby foods of 23.5, 7.5 and 0.9 µg/kg bw/day respectively (EFSA, 2005a, b and c). These exposures would not exceed the respective TDIs.

55. Phthalates are negative in the LLNA and guinea pig maximisation test and the evidence from human exposure is that they lack significant sensitisation potential (Medeiros et al., 1999; Geier et al., 2004, Kimber and Dearman, 2010). On the basis of patch-testing, contact dermatitis was attributed to four phthalates in 11 out of 388 workers at a polyvinyl chloride factory (Vidovic et al., 1985). No identified reports have indicated allergenicity from dietary exposure to phthalates. It has been suggested that any experimental evidence demonstrating an effect of exposure to phthalates on immune or allergic responses would be attributable to adjuvant properties, rather than immunogenicity

(Bornehag et al., 2010; Hansen et al., 2007; Kimber and Dearman, 2010). Kimber and Dearman (2010) concluded that there is no evidence to suggest that these chemicals have a consistent and proven ability to enhance allergic sensitisation under conditions of exposure that are relevant for human health.

56. The Committee concluded that while further data on infant exposures to phthalates would be desirable, it was not a high priority since estimated dietary exposures exceeded the TDIs only when very conservative approaches were adopted (i.e. using the highest identified mean concentration in powdered formula from a survey across 27 countries). On balance, the Committee considered that the evidence assembled indicated no special risks to infants, and that further evaluation of phthalates in the infant diet was not required at present.

Bisphenol A

57. Bisphenol A (BPA) was selected for evaluation because it has been used in the manufacture of infant feeding bottles and food containers and concerns have been raised about its endocrine modulation potential. The toxicity of BPA has been reviewed extensively by several authorities and a risk of adverse effects in infants from exposure to BPA has not been identified (EFSA, 2006a, 2008, 2010). Moreover, in January 2011, on a precautionary basis, the use of BPA in polycarbonate infant feeding bottles and the importation of such products was restricted in the European Union (EU) (EC, 2011).

58. A TDI of 50 µg/kg bw/day was set by EFSA (EFSA, 2006a), based on a NOAEL of 5 mg/kg bw/day in a two-generation reproductive toxicity study in mice and an uncertainty factor of 100.

59. Total (free and conjugated) and free BPA in breast milk of Japanese women has been reported at mean levels of 3.44 (SD 0.13) ng/mL (Kuroto-Niwa et al., 2007) and 0.61 (SD 0.21) ng/mL (Sun et al., 2004) respectively. For an infant body weight of 5 kg, the higher of these values would imply exposures of 0.55 µg/kg bw/day for an average consumer (800 mL), and 0.83 µg/kg bw/day for a high consumer (1200 mL). These are substantially lower than the TDI of 50 µg/kg bw/day.

60. Concentrations of BPA in liquid infant formula as a consequence of migration from infant feeding bottles have been reported to be typically about 10 µg/L, but as high as 50 µg/L in some cases (EFSA, 2006a). With these levels, the estimated daily dietary exposures of a 3 month old infant would be 1.6 and 8.0 µg/kg bw per day for an average consumer (800 mL) rising to 2.4 and 12.0 µg/kg bw per day for a high consumer (1200 mL).

61. BPA was detected in six brands of canned powdered formula milk and follow-up formula milk available on the market in Taiwan, with a maximum concentration of 113 µg/kg (Kuo and Ding, 2004; EFSA, 2006a). With the reconstitution value of 135 g/L indicated by the authors, average and high level consumption (800 and 1200 mL) would result in exposures of 2.44 and 3.66 µg/kg bw/day, respectively. With allowance also for the BPA that could migrate from infant feeding bottles, these data from Taiwan indicate that total exposures from formula feeding could be as high as 16 µg/kg bw/day in a high consumer. This is below the TDI of 50 µg/kg bw.

62. With regard to the weaning diet, EFSA estimated the dietary exposure of infants aged 6-12 months using data on the consumption of commercial baby foods and drinks reported for infants in Germany (EFSA, 2006a). At a high assumed concentration of BPA

in such products (100 µg BPA/kg), which EFSA noted was rarely exceeded, the potential dietary exposure from commercial baby foods and drinks was estimated to be 5.2 µg BPA/kg bw/day for a 7.8 kg infant aged 6 months. This again is well below the TDI.

63. Further possible sources of BPA exposure for this age group are polycarbonate tableware and polycarbonate receptacles used for the storage of food. Even with consumption of 52 g of food/kg bw per day (the 95th percentile for food consumption identified by EFSA for German infants at age 6 months), the highest reported level of BPA produced by migration from polycarbonate tableware into food simulants (5 µg BPA/kg), would give an estimated dietary exposure of only 0.3 µg BPA/kg bw/day (EFSA, 2006a).

64. Bisphenol A is not considered to be a significant allergen (Jolanki et al., 1995). No reports of allergenicity to BPA from dietary exposure were identified.

65. Given that the estimated dietary exposures of infants to BPA are well below the TDI, and the likelihood that in the future, their exposures will decline to even lower levels as a consequence of reduced use of BPA, the Committee concluded that no dietary advice was needed at present to protect against health risks from BPA in infants. However, this conclusion should be reviewed after the publication of an EFSA re-evaluation of BPA, which is currently ongoing.

Legacy pesticides

66. A number of bio-persistent pesticides that were banned during the 1980s and 1990s are still present in the environment and food chain. These compounds (aldrin, dieldrin, endrin, chlordane, heptachlor, hexachlorobenzene, mirex, toxaphene and DDT) are known collectively as legacy pesticides. All are classified as POPs. Although they are persistent in the environment, their levels have decreased since they ceased to be used. Few recent data are available on levels in breast milk, infant formula or infant food, possibly because they are now considered to be of less concern.

67. In Denmark, levels of dieldrin (a metabolite of aldrin) in breast milk were reported to decline from a mean of 1.33 µg/kg of milk in 1982 to 0.85 µg/kg of milk in 1986 (National Board of Health, 1987). More recently, daily intake of aldrin from food in adults and children was calculated to lie in the range from 1 to 10 ng/kg b.w. (EFSA, 2005d). This is substantially below the provisional tolerable daily intake (PTDI) of 100 ng/kg b.w. established by the Joint FAO/WHO Meeting on Pesticide Residues (JMPR) (WHO, 1995).

68. EFSA concluded that dietary exposures of adults and children to endrin were below 1 ng/kg b.w. (EFSA, 2005e), which is much lower than the PTDI of 200 ng/kg b.w. that had been established by JMPR (WHO, 1995). No data were found on levels of endrin in breast milk.

69. Reports often consider chlordane and heptachlor together, since technical-grade products of each compound contain about 10-20% of the other. No data were found on levels of chlordane in breast milk. However, current exposures from food have been estimated at two to three orders of magnitude below the PTDI of 500 ng/kg b.w. established by the WHO in 1995 (EFSA, 2007). In the 1970s, heptachlor was reported to be present in breast milk at levels ranging from 2 to 720 ng/g fat (IARC, 2001), whereas later surveys in the USA indicated a mean concentration of 10 ng/g fat (90th percentile 100 ng/g fat) (Rogan et al., 1991).

70. Reducing concentrations of hexachlorobenzene in breast milk have been widely reported. In Sweden, levels have been reported to decline from approximately 120 ng/g fat in 1972 to 10 ng/g fat in 1997 (Noren and Meryonite, 2000), while in Germany levels fell from 500 ng/g fat in 1983 to 190 ng/g fat in 1991 (Fürst et al., 1994). Studies conducted in Belgium, Canada, Denmark, the Netherlands and Switzerland have also indicated that levels of hexachlorobenzene in breast milk are decreasing (Jensen et al., 1991). The median concentration of hexachlorobenzene for European countries in the third WHO human milk field study was 36 ng/g fat (Malisch et al., 2004). Assuming an average daily intake of 800 mL breast milk with a fat content of 3.5 %, and a hexachlorobenzene concentration of 36 µg/kg milk fat, an exclusively breastfed baby weighing 5 kg would have median daily intake of around 200 ng/kg b.w. per day. For a high consumer with a daily intake of 1200 mL breast milk, the median hexachlorobenzene intake would be approximately 302 ng/kg b.w. per day. These calculated exposures somewhat exceed the TDI of 170 ng/kg b.w./day set by WHO in 1997 (WHO, 1997). However, the exceedance is for only a short period (the duration of breastfeeding), and it is well-established that exposures decrease by two orders of magnitude through childhood into adulthood (EFSA, 2006b). As the risk of toxicity from hexachlorobenzene depends on long-term cumulative exposure, current levels of exposure from breast milk are not a concern.

71. Few studies have been conducted on levels of mirex in breast milk, and none in Europe. Surveys of US and Canadian populations only found trace amounts (Jensen et al., 1991). EFSA has not produced an opinion on this compound. WHO evaluated the chemical in 1984 and 1990, but did not establish a TDI (WHO, 1984; WHO, 1990). WHO concluded that whilst mirex may occur in breast milk, levels were very low (WHO, 1990).

72. In the few available studies on toxaphene, reported levels in breast milk were close to or below the limit of detection in Hong Kong (Hedley et al., 2010) and Nicaragua (Romero et al., 2000). A study in Canada showed a reduction in levels over time from the late 1980s to early 1990s (Newsome et al., 1999). The highest measured levels (12.1 ng/g fat) in the most recent set of data (1992) were from women living near to the Canadian Great Lakes. The corresponding estimated exposure for an average breast milk consumer (800 mL) with a body weight of 5 kg would be 68 ng/kg b.w. day, while that for a high consumer of breast milk (1200 mL) would be approximately 100 ng/kg b.w. day. Both values are below the TDI of 0.2 µg/kg bw per day established by Health Canada (Health Canada, 2003) and 0.35 µg/kg bw per day established by the California Environmental Protection Agency (CA EPA) (CA EPA, 2008). EFSA has not produced an opinion on this compound.

73. A meta-analysis of 130 studies on DDT levels in breast milk, which were performed worldwide between 1950 and 1996, led to the conclusion that there had been a decline in levels from 5000-10000 µg/kg in 1950 to 1000 µg/kg in 1996 (Smith, 1999). The median value for European countries in the third WHO human milk field study was 0.19 µg/g fat (Malisch et al., 2004). Assuming an average daily intake of 800 mL breast milk with a fat content of 3.5 %, this would imply an average daily intake of 1.1 µg/kg bw for an exclusively breastfed baby weighing 5 kg. A high consumer with a daily intake of 1200 mL breast milk would receive an exposure of 1.6 µg/kg bw per day. Both of these values are below the PTDI of 10 µg/kg bw established by JMPR (WHO, 2001).

74. No reports were found which suggested that any of the legacy pesticides were allergenic following dietary exposure.

75. The COT concluded that levels of legacy pesticides in breast milk were generally declining, and the available information did not indicate a concern for health.

Topics requiring further work

76. The COT decided that the other chemicals selected for review would require separate more detailed assessment. These will be the subject of further statements over the next 18 months. The chemicals concerned are:

- Vitamin A
- Aluminium
- Lead
- Soy phytoestrogens
- Brominated flame retardants, including polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDE), hexabromocyclododecanes (HBCDDs), tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA) and other phenols, and polybrominated biphenyls (PBBs)
- Environmental pollutants classified recently classified as POPs, i.e. α - and β -hexachlorocyclohexane, lindane (γ -hexachlorocyclohexane), chlordecone, pentachlorobenzene, perfluoro octane sulphonic acid salts and perfluoro octane sulphone fluoride, and technical endosulfan and its related isomers.

77. In addition, at the request of SACN, COT is currently evaluating the risks associated with high vitamin D intake in people of all ages, including infants.

78. As indicated above, the COT will also carry out a separate review of the evidence on dietary exposures in infants and subsequent risk of developing food allergy, and atopic and auto-immune disease.

Conclusions

79. Breastfed infants can be exposed to caffeine as a result of maternal consumption of caffeine-containing foods and beverages, but the available scientific evidence does not demonstrate a consequent health risk in infants. The available information does not provide a basis for refining the current Government advice that breastfeeding mothers should avoid drinking too much tea or coffee (only occasionally rather than every day).

80. Reported effects in breastfed babies from maternal consumption of alcohol support the Government's current advice that breastfeeding mothers should consume no more than 1 or 2 units of alcohol once or twice a week.

81. Estimates of infants' dietary exposures to methylmercury (MeHg) from breast milk, infant formula and weaning foods are all below the PTWI of 1.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw, indicating no need to strengthen current Government advice (to limit consumption of shark, swordfish and marlin). The COT noted that EFSA is currently evaluating MeHg, and that depending on EFSA's conclusions, further review of MeHg might be required.

82. Intakes of dioxins and dioxin-like compounds by infants exceed the TDI during breastfeeding. However, this is not an immediate concern since the effects of dioxins are related to cumulative body burden rather than to levels of recent external exposure, and dietary exposures decrease as the diet diversifies and the infant gains weight. Furthermore, the TDI is based on reproductive effects related to maternal body burden, and not on an effect in infants. Given the decreasing occurrence of dioxin-like chemicals in breast milk and the lower dietary exposures from the more varied diet after weaning, the available scientific evidence does not indicate a need to change current advice on

breastfeeding or other aspects of infant feeding in order to protect against these chemicals.

83. While further data on infant exposures to phthalates would be desirable, this is not a high priority since estimated dietary exposures exceed TDIs only when very conservative approaches to risk assessment are adopted. The available evidence does not indicate any special risks to infants.

84. Estimated dietary exposures of infants to BPA are well below the TDI, and it is likely that in the future, their exposures will decline to even lower levels as a consequence of reduced use of compound. Therefore, there is no scientific basis at present for dietary advice to protect against health risks from BPA in infants. However, this conclusion should be reviewed after the publication of an EFSA re-evaluation of BPA, which is currently ongoing.

85. Few recent data are available on levels of legacy pesticides in breast milk, infant formula or infant food. Levels in breast milk are generally declining, and the available information does not indicate a concern for health.

86. Possible health risks from infants' dietary exposure to aluminium, vitamin A, soy phytoestrogens, lead, environmental contaminants recently classified as persistent organic pollutants (PBDEs, HBCDDs, TBBPA, PBBs and other brominated flame retardants) require further evaluation, and will be the subject of separate COT statements.

87. Evidence concerning the influence of infant diet on risks of food allergy, and atopic and autoimmune disease also requires detailed evaluation, and again, will be addressed in a separate review.

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References

- Alcorn J, McNamara PJ. Pharmacokinetics in the newborn. (2003) *Adv Drug Deliv Rev.* **55**(5): 667-86.
- Aranda JV, Collinge JM, Zinman R, and Watters G. (1979). Maturation of caffeine elimination in infancy. *Archives of Disease in Childhood.* **54**: 946-949.
- Backstrand JR, Goodman AH, Allen LH, and Pelto GH. (2004). Pulque intake during pregnancy and lactation in rural Mexico: Alcohol and child growth from 1 to 57 months. *European Journal of Clinical Nutrition.* **58**: 1626-1634
- Bates MN, Thomson B, Garrett N. (2002). Reduction in organochlorine levels in the milk of New Zealand women. *Arch Environ Health.* **57**(6): 591-7.
- Berlin Jr CM., Denson HM., Daniel CH., and Ward RM. (1984). Disposition of dietary caffeine in milk, saliva and plasma of lactating women. *Pediatrics.*, **73**(1): 59-63.
- Björnberg K, Vahter M, Berglund B, Niklasson B, Blennow M, Sandborgh-Englund G (2005). Transport of Methylmercury and Inorganic Mercury to the Fetus and Breast-Fed Infant. *Environ Health Persp.* **113**(10): 1381-1385.
- Bornehag CG, Nanberg E. (2010). Phthalate exposure and asthma in children. *Int J Androl.* **33**(2): 333-45.
- California Environmental Protection Agency (CA EPA). (2008). Development of fish contaminant goals and advisory tissue levels for common contaminants in California sport fish: Chlordane, DDTs, Dieldrin, Methylmercury, PCBs, Selenium, and Toxaphene. <http://oehha.ca.gov/fish/gtlsv/pdf/FCGsATLs27June2008.pdf>
- Cao, X-L (2010). Phthalate esters in foods: sources, occurrence and analytical methods. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety.* **9**(1): 21-43.
- Cazeneuve C, Pons G, Rey E, Treluyer JM, Cresteil T, Thiroux G, D'Athis P, Olive G. (1994). Biotransformation of caffeine in human liver microsomes from foetuses, neonates, infants and adults. *Br J Clin Pharmacol.* **37**(5): 405-12.
- Chien Y, Huang Y, Hsu C, Chao JC., and Liu J. (2009). Maternal lactation characteristics after consumption of an alcoholic soup during the postpartum 'doing –the-month' ritual. *Public Health Nutr.* **12**(3): 382-8
- Dearman RJ, Basketter DA, Kimber I. (2012). Inter-relationships between different classes of chemical allergens. *J Appl Toxicol.* [Epub ahead of print]
- EFSA (2005a). Opinion of the scientific panel on food additives, flavourings, processing aids and materials in contact with food (AFC) related to bis(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (DEHP) for use in food contact materials. *The EFSA Journal.* **243**: 1-20.
- EFSA (2005b). Opinion of the scientific panel on food additives, flavourings, processing aids and material in contact with food (afc) on a request from the commission related to di-butylphthalate (DBP) for use in food contact materials. *The EFSA Journal.* **242**: 1-17.
- EFSA (2005c). Opinion of the scientific panel on food additives, flavourings, processing aids and materials in contact with food (AFC) on a request from the Commission related to butylbenzylphthalate (BBP) for use in food contact materials. *The EFSA Journal.* **241**: 1-14.

- EFSA (2005d). Opinion of the scientific panel on contaminants in the food chain [CONTAM] related to aldrin and dieldrin as undesirable substance in animal feed. *The EFSA Journal*. **285**: 1–43.
- EFSA. (2005e). Opinion of the scientific panel on contaminants in the food chain [CONTAM] related to endrin as undesirable substance in animal feed. *The EFSA Journal*. **286**: 1–31.
- EFSA (2006a). Opinion of the scientific panel on food additives, flavourings, processing aids and materials in contact with food on a request from the commission related to 2,2-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)propane (bisphenol A). *The EFSA Journal*. **428**: 1-75
- EFSA (2006b). Opinion of the scientific panel on contaminants in the food chain on a request from the commission related to hexachlorobenzene as undesirable substance in animal feed. *The EFSA Journal*. **402**: 1–49.
- EFSA. (2007). Chlordane as undesirable substance in animal feed. Scientific panel on contaminants in the food chain. *The EFSA Journal*. **582**, 1-53.
- EFSA, (2008). Scientific opinion of the panel on food additives, flavourings, processing aids and materials in contact with food (AFC). Toxicokinetics of bisphenol A. *The EFSA Journal* **759**: 1-10
- EFSA, (2010). Scientific opinion on bisphenol A: evaluation of a study investigating its neurodevelopmental toxicity, review of recent scientific literature on its toxicity and advice on the Danish risk assessment of bisphenol A of the EFSA panel on food contact materials, enzymes, flavourings and processing aids (CEF) on request from the European Commission. *The EFSA Journal*. **8**(1829): 1–116.
- EFSA. (2011). Scientific opinion on polybrominated diphenyl ether in food. *The EFSA Journal* **9**(5): 1-274.
- EFSA (2012). Scientific report of EFSA. Update of the monitoring of levels of dioxins and PCBs in food and feed. *The EFSA Journal*. **10**(7): 1-82.
- Fromme H., Gruber L., Seckin E., Raab U., Zimmermann S., Kiranoglu M., Schlummer M., Schwegler U., Smolic S. and Volkel W. (2011). Phthalates and their metabolites in breast milk – results from the Bavarian Monitoring of Breast Milk (BAMBI). *Environment International*. **37**(4): 715-22
- FSA, (2006). Survey of metals in weaning foods and formulae for infants- additional information on inorganic arsenic and methyl mercury levels. <http://www.food.gov.uk/multimedia/pdfs/fsis0703.pdf>
- FSA, (2012). Determination of phthalates in foods and establishing methodology to distinguish their source. http://www.foodbase.org.uk/admin/tools/reportdocuments/740-1-1258_C01048_phthalates.pdf
- Fürst P, Fürst C, Wilmers K. (1994). Human milk as a bioindicator for body burden of PCDDs, PCDFs, organochlorine pesticides, and PCBs. *Environ Health Persp*. **102**: 187-93.
- Fürst P. (2006). Dioxins, polychlorinated biphenyls and other organohalogen compounds in human milk. Levels, correlations, trends and exposure through breastfeeding. *Mol Nutr Food Res*. **50**(10): 922-33.
- Geier J, Lessmann H, Dickel H, Frosch PJ, Kock P, Becker D, Jappe U, Aberer W, Schnuch A, Uter W. (2004). Patch test results with metalworking fluid series of the German Contact Dermatitis Research Group (DKG). *Contact Derm* **51**: 118-30.

- Giglia R., and Binns C. (2006). Alcohol and lactation: A systematic review. *Nutrition and Dietetics*. **63**: 103-116.
- Hansen JS, Larsen ST, Poulsen LK, Nielsen GD. (2007). Adjuvant effects of inhaled mono-2-ethylhexyl phthalate in BALB/cJ mice. *Toxicology*. **232**(1-2): 79-88
- Health Canada (2003). Human Health – Canadian Arctic contaminants assessment report II. http://www.ainc-inac.gc.ca/ncp/pub/pdf/hea/hea_e.pdf
- Hedley AJ, Hui LL, Kypke K, Malisch R, van Leeuwen FX, Moy G, Wong TW, Nelson EA. (2010). Residues of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) in human milk in Hong Kong. *Chemosphere*. **79**(3): 259-65.
- Hildebrandt R, Gundert-Remy U. (1983). Lack of pharmacological active saliva levels of caffeine in breast-fed infants. *Pediatr Pharmacol (New York)*. **3**: 237-44.
- Högberg J, Hanberg A, Berglund M, Skerfving S, Remberger M, Calafat AM, Filipsson AF, Jansson B, Johansson N, Appelgren M, Håkansson H. (2008). Phthalate diesters and their metabolites in human breast milk, blood or serum, and urine as biomarkers of exposure in vulnerable populations. *Environ Health Persp*. **116**(3): 334-9
- Hultman P, Hansson-Georgiadis H. (1999). Methyl mercury-induced autoimmunity in mice. *Toxicol Appl Pharmacol* **154**: 203-11.
- Ikarashi Y, Tsuchiya T, Nakamura A. (1992). Detection of contact sensitivity of metal salts using the murine local lymph node assay. *Toxicol Lett* **62**: 53-61.
- Jensen AA, Slorach SA. (1991). Chemical contaminants in human milk. Boca Raton, Florida. CRC press. ISBN. 0849366070.
- Jolanki R, Kanerva L, Estlander T. (1995). Occupational allergic contact dermatitis caused by epoxy diacrylate in ultraviolet-light-cured paint, and bisphenol A in dental composite resin. *Contact Dermatitis*. **33**: 94-9.
- Kalow W, Tang BK. The use of caffeine for enzyme assays: a critical appraisal. (1993) *Clin Pharmacol Ther*. **53**(5): 503-14.
- Kimber I, Dearman RJ. (2010). An assessment of the ability of phthalates to influence immune and allergic responses. *Toxicology*. **271**: 73-82.
- Kimber I, Basketter DA, Gerberick GF, Ryan CA, Dearman RJ. (2011). Chemical allergy: translating biology into hazard characterization. *Toxicol Sci*. **120**: S238-68.
- Kunisue T, Muraoka M, Ohtake M, Sudaryanto A, Minh NH, Ueno D, Higaki Y, Ochi M, Tsydenova O, Kamikawa S, Tonegi T, Nakamura Y, Shimomura H, Nagayama J, Tanabe S. (2006). Contamination status of persistent organochlorines in human breast milk from Japan: recent levels and temporal trend. *Chemosphere*. **64**(9): 1601-8.
- Kuo H.W. Ding W.H. (2004). Trace determination of bisphenol A and phytoestrogens in infant formula powders by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. *Journal of chromatography. A*. **1027**(1-2): 67-74
- Kuroto-Niwa R., Tateoka Y., Usuki Y. and Nozawa R. (2007). Measurement of bisphenol A concentrations in human colostrum. *Chemosphere*. **66**(6): 1160-4.
- Lundberg K, Grönvik KO, Dencker L. (1991). 2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin (TCDD) induced suppression of the local immune response. *Int J Immunopharmacol*. **13**: 357-68.
- Malisch R, Kypke K, van Leeuwen R. and Moy G. (2004). Unpublished data from the 3rd WHO human milk field study.

- Medeiros AM, Devlin DJ, Keller LH. (1999). Evaluation of skin sensitization response of dialkyl (C₆-C₉) phthalate esters. *Contact Derm.* **41**: 287-90.
- Mennella JA., and Beauchamp GK. (1991). The transfer of alcohol to human milk: effects on flavour and the infants' behaviour. *The New England Journal of Medicine.* **325**(14): 981-985.
- Mortz CG, Lauritsen JM, Bindslev-Jensen C, Andersen KE. (2002). Nickel sensitization in adolescents and association with ear piercing, use of dental braces and hand eczema. The odense adolescence cohort study on atopic diseases and dermatitis (TOACS). *Acta Derm Venereol* **82**: 359-64.
- National Board of Health (1987) *Dioxins in mothers' milk.* Copenhagen, National Board of Health. Hygeijne meddelelser 7.
- Newsome WH, Ryan JJ. (1999). Toxaphene and other chlorinated compounds in human milk from northern and southern Canada: a comparison. *Chemosphere.* **39**(3): 519-26.
- Norén K, Meironyté D. (2000). Certain organochlorine and organobromine contaminants in Swedish human milk in perspective of past 20-30 years. *Chemosphere.* **40**(9-11): 1111-23.
- Pelkonen O, Katiala EH, Larmi TKI, Karlu NT. (1973). Comparison of activities of drug metabolizing enzymes in human fetal and adult livers. *Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics.* **14**: 840-6.
- Polder A, Odland JO, Tkachev A, Føreid S, Savinova TN, Skaare JU. (2003). Geographic variation of chlorinated pesticides, toxaphenes and PCBs in human milk from sub-arctic and arctic locations in Russia. *Sci Total Environ.* **306**(1-3): 179-95.
- Polder A, Thomsen C, Lindström G, Løken KB, Skaare JU. (2008). Levels and temporal trends of chlorinated pesticides, polychlorinated biphenyls and brominated flame retardants in individual human breast milk samples from Northern and Southern Norway. *Chemosphere.* **73**(1): 14-23.
- Raab U, Preiss U, Albrecht M, Shahin N, Parlar H, Fromme H. (2008). Concentrations of polybrominated diphenyl ethers, organochlorine compounds and nitro musks in mother's milk from Germany (Bavaria). *Chemosphere.* **72**(1): 87-94.
- Rogan WJ, Blanton PJ, Portier CJ, Stallard E. (1991) Should the presence of carcinogens in breast milk discourage breast feeding? *Regul. Toxicol. Pharmacol.*, **13**: 228-240.
- Romero ML, Dorea JG, Granja AC. (2000). Concentrations of organochlorine pesticides in milk of Nicaraguan mothers. *Arch Environ Health.* **55**(4): 274-8.
- Ryu J. E. (1985a). Caffeine in human milk and in serum of breast-fed infants. *Dev. Pharmacol. Ther.* **8**: 329-337.
- Ryu J. E. (1985b). Effect of maternal caffeine consumption on heart rate and sleep time of breast-fed infants. *Dev. Pharmacol. Ther.* **8**: 355-363.
- Sakamoto M, Kubota M, Matsumoto S, Nakano A and Akagi H. (2002). Declining risk of methylmercury exposure to infants during lactation. *Environmental Research.* **90**: 185-189.
- Smith D. (1999). Worldwide trends in DDT levels in human breast milk.. *Int. J. Epidemiol.* **28**(2): 179-188.
- Smith-Sivertsen T, Tchachtchine V, Lund E. (2002). Environmental nickel pollution: does it protect against nickel allergy? *J Am Acad Dermatol* **46**: 460-2.

- Stiller-Winkler R, Radaszkiewicz T, Gleichmann E. (1988). Immunopathological signs in mice treated with mercury compounds-I. Identification by the popliteal lymphnode assay of responder and nonresponder strains. *Int J Immunopharmacol* **10**: 475-84.
- Sun Y, Irie M, Kishikawa N, Wada M, Kuroda N, Nakashima K. (2004). Determination of bisphenol A in human breast milk by HPLC with column-switching and fluorescence detection. *Biomed Chromatogr.* **18**: 501-7.
- Tyrala E. E., and Dodson W. E. (1979). Caffeine secretion into breast milk. *Archives of Disease in Childhood.* **54**: 787-789.
- Ulaszewska MM, Zuccato E, Davoli E. (2011). PCDD/Fs and dioxin-like PCBs in human milk and estimation of infants' daily intake: a review. *Chemosphere.* **83**(6): 774-82.
- Van Hoogstraten IM, Andersen KE, Von Blomberg BM, Boden D, Bruynzeel DP, Burrows D, Camarasa JG, Doms-Goossens A, Kraal G, Lahti A, et al. (1991). Reduced frequency of nickel allergy upon oral nickel contact at an early age. *Clin Exp Immunol.* **85**: 441-5.
- Van Leeuwen FXR, Malish R. (2002). Results of the third round of WHO-coordinated exposure study on the levels of PCBs, PCDDs and PCDFs in human milk. *Organohalogen Compounds.* **56**: 311-316.
- Vidović R, Kansky A. (1985). Contact dermatitis in workers processing polyvinyl chloride plastics. *Derm Beruf Umwelt.* **33**(3): 104-5.
- World Health Organization (1984). *Mirex. IPCS Environmental Health Criteria* **44**. <http://www.inchem.org/documents/ehc/ehc/ehc44.htm>
- World Health Organization (1990). *Mirex. IPCS Health and Safety guide* **39**. <http://www.inchem.org/documents/hsg/hsg/hsg039.htm>
- World Health Organization (1995). Pesticide residues in food — 1994. Report of the Joint Meeting of the FAO Panel of Experts on Pesticide Residues in Food and the Environment and WHO Toxicological and Environmental Core Assessment Groups (FAO Plant Production and Protection Paper 127).
- World Health Organisation (1997). Hexachlorobenzene. *Environmental Health Criteria* **195** –; ISBN 92 4157195. ISSN 0250-863X
- World Health Organisation (2001) *Pesticide residues in food — 2000. Evaluations — 2000. Part II — Toxicology*. Joint FAO/WHO Meeting on Pesticide Residues (WHO/PCS/01.3).
- World Health Organisation (2003). Diethyl Phthalate. Concise International Chemical Assessment Document 52. <http://www.who.int/ipcs/publications/cicad/en/cicad52.pdf>
- World Health Organisation. (2009). Principles and methods for the risk assessment of chemicals in food. *Environmental Health Criteria* 240.

Abbreviations

BBP	Butylbenzyl phthalate
BPA	Bisphenol A
COT	Committee on Toxicity of Chemicals in Food, Consumer Products and the Environment
DBP	Dibutyl phthalate
DEHP	Diethylhexyl phthalate
DEP	Diethyl phthalate
DIBP	Diisobutyl phthalate
DDT	Dichlorodiphenyl trichloroethane
DH	Department of Health
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FSA	Food Standards Agency
GEMS/Food	Global Environment Monitoring System/Food
Ig E	Immunoglobulin E
TDS	Total Diet Study
TEF	Toxic Equivalency Factor
I-TEQ	International Toxic Equivalent
JECFA	Joint FAO/WHO Committee on Food Additives
JMPR	Joint FAO/WHO Meeting on Pesticide Residues
LLNA	Local Lymph Node Assay
LOD	Limit of Detection
MeHg	Methylmercury
PCDD	Polychlorinated dibenzodioxins
PCDF	Polychlorinated dibenzofurans
POPs	Persistent Organic Pollutants
PTDI	Provisional Tolerable Daily Intake
PTWI	Provisional Tolerable Weekly Intake
SACN	Scientific Advisory Committee on Nutrition
SD	Standard Deviation
TDI	Tolerable Daily Intake
US EPA	United States Environmental Protection Agency
WHO	World Health Organisation